

AIRFRAME - Fast prototyping framework for UAVs definition

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Abstract—Developing a new UAV platform is a long and iterative process that requires a lot of time and effort to be successful. The difficulty of performing a realistic evaluation of system performance during the development process represents a major drawback. As a matter of fact, in most contexts, the first proof of UAVs’ capabilities arrives only during the first flights of the real platform. This may lead, in case of possible issues detected in the platform, to a reevaluation of the design, which is not optimal at the very last stage of platform development. To overcome this issue, we propose AIRFRAME, a framework for fast-developing UAV prototypes in simulation to allow for systematic evaluation and analysis of UAV performance during the development process. The developed prototype integrates software and hardware for a better evaluation of the system’s capability and performance at an early stage. The implementation of the framework has succeeded with Gazebo-ROS-Matlab in Docker Environment. It allows high integrability and fast evaluation of multiple UAV designs.

Index Terms—fast prototyping, simulation, docker

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years multi-rotor UAVs have been experiencing constant growth in academics and industry. Due to their maneuverability and flexibility, they represent a suitable solution for different fields on the market, such as civil and military. Today UAVs are required to perform more and more complex tasks, such as inspecting, navigating autonomously into the environment, and carrying objects. From a hardware and software perspective, it implies the design and the integration of many sensors and devices into a UAV platform, which still needs to remain a quite small solution. Indeed, the overall development of these platforms has become quite a complex challenge, with many engineers involved in the process. To help them in the development, flight simulators specific to UAVs have been developed in recent years. Some open-source simulators are available today such as RotorS [4], MRS UAV system [3] and Flightmare [5]. Many engineers have used them in universities and industry for the study and design of these platforms. They are usually composed of three main elements: a physics engine, such as Gazebo, AirSim, or Unreal engine, a communication layer, ROS and Mavlink, and commercial autopilot, such as PX4 or Ardupilot for the embedded control

design. On top of this architecture, developers typically design further software components, such as planning algorithms or image recognition, to extend and enhance the functionality of the system. The overall main reason behind the adoption of a UAV simulator is to test those components in a safe environment before integrating them into the real system. As a consequence, general simulators are usually deployed for standard UAV platforms like Crazyflie or DJI frames (e.g. f450, f550) or quasi-standard platforms. There is a lack of presence for an overall system simulation, that includes both hardware and software. However, the possibility of having a complete prototype of the developed platform could be helpful, especially during the development process of a new UAV platform, because it could allow testing different design solutions and evaluating their performance without assembling them. Some efforts in this direction have been done in [2] and [1], where some approaches are presented towards the creation of digital prototypes through the UAV development process, although they are limited to specific platforms or use cases. Here we propose AIRFRAME, a new framework that enables the quick creation of complete prototypes for custom UAV platforms and offers the capability for fast development and deployment of flight controllers using Matlab/Simulink. The proposed framework combines hardware and software components to provide an effective solution to evaluate system performance and test algorithms in flight. The integration of a flight controller, designed using Simulink, offers benefits such as faster integration with hardware components and easier debugging capabilities, as well as compatibility with the Robot Operating System (ROS) and Gazebo, the chosen simulation platform. Additionally, adopting Docker helps avoid dependency issues and enhances the scalability and adoption of the system. This aims at reducing the time of developing a new multi-rotor platform by providing a fast solution to testing UAVs prototypes developed along the way, as shown in Figure 1. Therefore, with AIRFRAME, we create a simulated scenario where we can test the drone before the creation of the actual platform so that, if any critical issue arise during test, we can make some design changes to the platform and fast retest it using AIRFRAME. This approach can save time and resources compared to the traditional one, which requires the testing of the physical UAV, and allows users to explore different design variations and configurations in a safe and controlled environment. With this the main contribution of the paper can be summarized as follows:

- efficiency improvement of the standard development pro-

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cess of UAV platforms based on systematic simulation assessment

- fast design and deployment of flight controllers for UAVs (with flat and tilting propellers) for ROS-based environment

Thus the paper is organized as follows: in section II we presented the general problem, the designed approach used for the framework, and a description of various subsystems. In section III we presented the design approach for the flight controller, as well as communication with the simulator and the docker implementation. Finally, some practical applications of the framework are proposed in section IV and the conclusion is outlined in section V.

Fig. 1. A comparison between *Standard Development Process* (right) and *Airframe Development Process* (left) of UAV platforms. The addition of a hardware-software prototype in the process (in red) allows for an evaluation of platforms at early stages for a faster and more agile development process.

II. AIRFRAME ARCHITECTURE

A. Problem statement

Developing and testing new UAV platforms is a long and iterative process, that requires a significant amount of resources and time. As illustrated in Figure 1, a standard development process is composed of five main stages: a requirements analysis is performed to establish the performance specifications for the UAV, which are defined in accordance with its intended mission. After that, the UAV design phase begins, where the first prototype of the UAV is designed, usually with the help of Computer-aided-design (CAD) programs. After the design of the mechanical model, the assembly process begins, where

the actual UAV is assembled. Completed this phase, control algorithms (such as flight controller, trajectory planning, etc) are integrated and then the flight test campaign begins to evaluate and prove the performance of the system. As it is possible to notice, one of the main issues of the explained process is the possibility to evaluate the real capability of the system only during flight tests. If any major issue or any platform's limitation is encountered a reevaluation of the design must be performed and the whole process restarts again. As a consequence, *the standard development* described results in a long, iterative and constrained process that is not time optimal and it is not very flexible towards platform changes after the assembly of the first prototype is achieved. It's important to remark that changes during the development process are quite normal for UAVs, because designing a new platform is a complex process, especially due to the number of subsystems that must be integrated (e.g arm devices, embedded pc, camera, etc) and the obvious limitations of the platform in terms of size and weight. Due to this, it's not rare to encounter platform limitations or mechanical issues only during its actual flight. To minimize this aspect, it becomes essential the possibility of a fast and continuous evaluation of UAV design during the whole development process to better assist engineers. To this aim, in the proposed framework an early-stage prototype is designed, which integrates both hardware and the software of the under-development platform. This implies a systematic simulation-based robot assessment during the whole development process, which allows engineers to fast evaluate new changes in the platform and to test multiple design choices in an optimal way. This results in a constant evaluation of the requirement elaborated in the first stage, minimizing the possibility of design reevaluation at the last stages of the development process.

B. Concept

The concept behind the presented framework is to utilize information from the mechanical design, the actuator units, the sensor, and the flight control to create detailed UAV prototypes. The result, as proposed in Figure 2, is the fast creation of detailed UAV prototypes in a simulation environment for a systematic evaluation and verification of its performance during the development process.

Fig. 2. AIRFRAME architecture map.

1) *Robot model*: During the design of a new unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) frame, generally CAD are utilized to help the engineers develop a complete model of the first prototypes. The 3D generated model contains a complete overview of the prototype, including the frame, propellers, additional devices, etc. This allows an efficient and accurate visualization of the design and easy modification of each component and the overall frame, leading to a more optimized final product. Furthermore, many CAD software allows for performing further analysis on the developed structure, such as stress analysis and estimate of UAV parameters, which are necessary for the scope of the proposed framework. The information collected for the CAD model, i.e. mass, inertia, and geometry of various components, are integrated into a simulation environment for a realistic evaluation of the prototype.

2) *Physical Simulator Engine*: To perform simulation scenarios to evaluate system capability a Physical Simulator Engine is necessary. Different simulation environments are known within the UAV research community, such as Gazebo, AirSim, or V-rep (also known as CoppeliaSim) [8]. Among the available solutions, we decide to use Gazebo as a Simulation environment, thanks to its compatibility with ROS and Simulink, as later explained in section II-C.

With the information provided by the CAD model, a model can be then generated in the simulator. The generated model can be considered, for a standard UAV platform a 6Dof rigid body, as exposed in [9] and [10]. The overall dynamics equation can then be considered as:

$$m\dot{v} = R_B F_B, \quad (1a)$$

$$J\dot{\omega}_B = M_B - \omega_B \times J\omega_B \quad (1b)$$

where \dot{v} corresponds to the acceleration vector expressed in the inertial frame, R_B represents the rotation matrix from the body frame to the inertial frame, J the inertial frame matrix, M_B is the moment in the body frame and ω_B the angular velocity in the same frame.

While the presented model can be considered suitable for conventional platforms such as DJI Mavic or Parrot Anafi, its applicability to unconventional platforms, such as those presented in [11] or [12], may be limited. The increasing number of degrees of freedom in these platforms results in a more complex system's model, which poses challenges in deriving a comprehensive mathematical equation for flight controller design.

3) *Power system*: After the creation of the simulated prototype, utilizing information from the CAD model in the proposed simulated environment, a power system must be merged into the prototype for a complete simulation of its flying capability. From the requirement specifications, an estimate of the power required by the platform is provided, typically obtained from the weight requirements. From these requirements, the model of the rotor is selected. This information must be merged into the developed prototype. A general model

to simulate the rotors' actuation can be considered as:

$$F_i = c_f K_f \omega_i^2 \quad (2a)$$

$$\tau_i = c_m K_m \omega_i^2 \quad (2b)$$

where F_i and τ_i represent respectively the force and the torque generated by the i -th rotor, K_f and K_m the lift force coefficient and the drag torque coefficient, ω_i the rotor velocity of the i -th propeller. c_f and c_m represent two coefficients between 0 and 1 to take into account loss in performance.

In recent years, the use of actuators in UAVs has become widespread, used for different varieties of subsystems such as gimbals to stabilize cameras or robotic arms to perform contact flight. To address these configurations, we add the possibility to integrate actuators as well into the prototypes. Therefore a servo model and its controller are designed in AIRFRAME to ensure compatibility with a wider range of UAV platforms. In particular, the servo has been modelled as a first-order system with some limitations on its angle:

$$\theta = \frac{1}{s\tau + 1} \theta_{ref} \quad \theta \in (\theta_{min}, \theta_{max}) \quad (3)$$

θ represents the actual servo angle, θ_{ref} the reference angle from the controller, while τ , θ_{min} and θ_{max} are parameters to set to modify the settling time, the maximum servo angle and the minimum servo angle respectively. The reference servo angle is provided by a PID controller to control and stabilize the power system.

4) *Simulate sensors*: To complete the prototype of the design, the sensor must be integrated into the platform, to generate better data for performance analysis and for the design of the flight controller, as explained in section III. Modern UAVs can carry a wide variety of sensors depending on many factors such as autonomy level, tasks required by the UAV, and safety considerations. Indeed prototypes should be able to carry the needed sensors as well for a setup evaluation and to have a complete prototype upon which testing algorithms are designed by the software team. Here we are going to present a couple of sensors, IMU, and odometry, which can be considered a basic setup to then integrate a flight controller to enable the flight. Although further sensor models can be added to the prototype depending on the application. *IMU*. The IMU sensor attached to the UAV main body provides a 3-axis accelerometer and 3-axis gyroscope in the body frame. As proposed by [13] and [6], to create more realistic results the true values are affected by two sources of error, the intrinsic noise of the sensor $\beta_{acc,\omega}$ that follows a Gaussian distribution and some biases $\alpha_{acc,\omega}$ modelled as random walk noise (the derivative of the biases follow a Gaussian noise distribution).

$$a_{meas} = a_{real} + \beta_{acc} + n_{acc} \quad (4a)$$

$$\omega_{meas} = \omega_{real} + \beta_{\omega} + n_{beta} \quad (4b)$$

$$\beta_{acc} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_a^2), \beta_{\omega} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\omega}^2) \quad (4c)$$

$$\dot{n}_{acc} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\alpha_{acc}}^2), \dot{n}_{\omega} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\alpha_{\omega}}^2) \quad (4d)$$

with a_{real} and ω_{real} being the real acceleration and angular rate and a_{meas} and ω_{meas} the measured ones.

Odometry. An odometry sensor attached to the UAV body provides its current position with respect to the global frame. For its model, it can be considered as a measurement affected by white noise disturbances:

$$\begin{aligned} x_{meas} &= x_{real} + \gamma_x \\ y_{meas} &= y_{real} + \gamma_y \\ z_{meas} &= z_{real} + \gamma_z \end{aligned} \quad (5a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} v_{meas} &= \dot{x}_{meas} \\ \gamma_x &\sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_x^2), \gamma_y \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_y^2), \gamma_z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_z^2) \end{aligned} \quad (5b)$$

$(x_{meas}, y_{meas}, z_{meas})$ represents the measured quantities along each axis, $(x_{real}, y_{real}, z_{real})$ the real values and γ represents a white noise added disturbance. The velocity is computed from the derivation from the position.

This standard sensor setup allows for complete integration with the flight controller without the necessity of an estimator to compute the actual position of the UAV. Although for more complex simulation scenarios, a state estimator should be considered to correctly evaluate the UAVs' position, orientation, and velocity.

5) *Control:* The prototype is developed in the framework merging the information available from all the components. Now for an evaluation of system capability, a flight controller must be integrated into it. The procedure for the design of the controller and its integration with all the other systems is introduced in section III and IV. The developed controllers will be created in Simulink, which permits fast integration with the other components.

C. AIRFRAME Implementation

The proposed architecture is developed using Matlab, ROS, Gazebo, and C++. In particular, Gazebo is used as a simulation environment, ROS for the communication within the various systems, Matlab for the development and deployment of the flight controller, and C++ to develop Sensor and Power System models for the prototypes.

The creation of the UAVs prototypes in Gazebo is performed with STL files and xacro files. The STL files contain information on the geometry of the UAVs while xacro files are necessary to mount the prototype together and to inject in the simulator the UAVs parameters (e.g mass and moment of inertia) estimated from the CAD model. The overall structure is recomposed in Gazebo connecting joints and links together, as shown in Figure 3. Furthermore, Gazebo allows us to add plugins, which are shared library that communicates directly with the physical engine and we use them to integrate the sensor model and power systems into the prototype. The models presented in section II (equations 2 and 4) are then implemented in C++ and integrated into the proposed simulator.

The implementation of the flight controller is achieved using Matlab. This choice is motivated by the possibility of fast design and easy debugging system capabilities. Furthermore,

Fig. 3. Sample of joint-link connection in Gazebo

the integration with AIRFRAME simulator will allow the usage of native Simulink Toolbox, such as Model Predictive Toolbox or UAV toolbox, for the design of guidance and control laws, simplifying the development process.

An overview of a flight controller integrated with the simulator is presented in Figure 4, as it is possible to notice that communication with all the entities mentioned so far is granted via Robotic Operating system (ROS). The communication and integration between ROS and Gazebo have been proven in many projects developed by the research community, such as [4]. Its integration with Gazebo is facilitated through packages such as ROS control and Gazebo plugins, which are used as well in our framework. As a result, integration ROS-Gazebo for AIRFRAME allows reading sensor data and sending the commands to rotors and actuators via ROS. The compatibility

Fig. 4. Flow of AIRFRAME for a generic multirotor UAV

between Simulink and ROS is also possible and it is granted via *ROS toolbox*, which is a Mathworks toolbox available for different ROS distro (also compatible with ROS2). It allows performing many actions available with ROS directly in Simulink (for example subscribing and publishing data to a topic or calling ROS services), enabling receiving data from the sensor and sending actuators commands to the power system, as illustrated in Figure 4. With the compatibility Simulink-ROS, we can design a controller in Simulink in such a way as to be considered as a ROS node. This has the benefit of better integration with other software components that are compatible with ROS. This aspect is particularly helpful during the deployment phase, where the flight controller runs directly on the UAV prototype (Figure 5).

To improve the efficiency and adaptability of AIRFRAME, we

integrate it with the Docker environment. As better illustrated in Figure 5, the overall framework has been adapted to deal with docker. In particular, from publicly available ROS images, a Dockerfile has been created to install AIRFRAME simulator with UAV prototypes and their dependencies. With this procedure, a docker image with AIRFRAME prototype running the Simulator and communicating with ROS has been created. To launch a flight test with the UAV prototype a container can be created with AIRFRAME docker image inside, and then the flight controller in Simulink can be launched from the host machine, it will send a command to the UAV using ROS. With AIRFRAME Docker configuration, we will ensure more flexibility and adaptability of the simulator, avoiding the installation of dependencies that may generate conflicts or issues on new machines.

III. FAST FLIGHT CONTROL PROTOTYPING

One of the advantages of AIRFRAME is the ability to fast test and debug UAVs prior to their actual deployment in a flight campaign. To this end, the design of a UAV flight control system is required to evaluate the performance of the system under different flight conditions. This section provides insight into the design and implementation of a flight control architecture for a platform developed under the proposed framework.

Many different control algorithms have been deployed for UAVs, such as Model Predictive Control (MPC) [23], optimal control techniques [24], geometric-based control strategies [17] or standard PID-based control [25]. An overview on the most important one is outlined in [15] and [16]. Among the many control proposed, LQR and PID control-based techniques have been the most widely used, although in recent years geometric control approach [17] has gained popularity in the research community for its robustness and its performance.

This section shows how a geometric-based flight control architecture could be implemented in Simulink and integrated with the simulator via ROS within the AIRFRAME context. The controller is based on the control design proposed in [17] adapted for the Simulink environment, the communication with the prototype is performed using ROS communication network. The choice to design the controller in Simulink guarantees fast integration and debugging, additionally it allows a full integration with ROS environment throughout *Matlab ROS system toolbox*, as shown in Figure 6. This gives higher flexibility to adopt the controller also during the deployment phase since it can be fully integrated and controlled as a "standard" ROS node.

Indeed during this phase, the developed flight controller is deployed in the embedded PC onboard the UAV using *Simulink Embedded Coder toolbox*, which generates a C++ ROS node from the Simulink model developed during the design phase (Figure 5).

IV. USE CASE AND SAMPLES

Some examples are provided to show the capabilities of AIRFRAME and to demonstrate its ability to work with differ-

Fig. 5. AIRFRAME architecture during the design phase (left) and deployment phase (right). In the **Design Phase**, the simulator is provided as a docker image, while the Flight Controller is running in Simulink in the Host Machine. The communication between the two is granted via TCP/IP protocol. In the **Deployment phase** the C++ version of the Final Flight Controller is deployed on the onboard PC on the UAV. The C++ code of the Flight Controller Simulink model has been auto-generated via *Simulink Embedded toolbox*.

Fig. 6. Example of geometric control integrated with AIRFRAME.

ent types of platforms and control systems. The goal of these examples is to demonstrate the flexibility and adaptability of AIRFRAME in various real-world scenarios. To achieve this, three different cases are considered, each highlighting a different aspect of AIRFRAME's capabilities. The first case is a standard commercial platform commonly used in different fields. This will demonstrate the compatibility of AIRFRAME with widely available and pre-built drone models and its ability to provide detailed simulations and control them efficiently. The second case is a custom UAV platform, in this scenario, special UAV designs are made by integrating custom models into commercial DJI frames (e.g DJI F550) with some custom model to fulfil specific tasks or environments. This case will highlight AIRFRAME's ability to work with these custom designs and adapt to their specific requirements and constraints.

Fig. 7. DJI M300 RTK in AIRFRAME simulator

Fig. 8. Flight test performed with DJI M300 RTK, after the integration of the flight controller and described in section III. The three plots provide the reference values (in blue) and the measured data (in black) of X position, Y position and Z position

The last case considers omnidirectional UAVs (OMAVs). OMAVs are a particular type of UAVs where multiple servos are integrated into the platform to allow a much larger set of motions with respect to standard UAVs. They are capable of flying in any direction without the need for a specific orientation. This case will underline AIRFRAME's ability to integrate servos into prototypes and to adapt to a particular class of UAVs.

A. Commercial platform

For the mentioned first case, we integrate a standard platform into the system. In particular, as reported in Figure 7, we use DJI M300 RTK. We create a prototype for the platform from the cad model following the procedure described in section II. An IMU and an odometry sensor have been mounted into the platform's prototype to provide data for stability control. The geometric control architecture developed in section III is integrated into the system, adjusting some parameters for the DJI platform. We perform some flights to check the performance and to evaluate the framework, data from a flight test are provided in Figure 8. The results indicate that the system is capable of stable hovering and successful execution of the user-defined trajectory with good accuracy.

The integration of AIRFRAME with a standard UAV platform has been proven feasible, offering a high level of compatibility and adaptability. It's important to note that in case there is the necessity to mount further devices on these platforms, such as

Fig. 9. AERO-CAM in AIRFRAME Simulator

lidar or cameras with gimbal, the integration can be carried out seamlessly and easily in AIRFRAME.

B. Custom platform

For the second case, a custom UAV platform is considered, AERO-CAM. AERO-CAM is a UAV designed to visually inspect large infrastructures, such as bridges or viaducts. In [18] a report on the system architecture and the platform application has been provided.

For the integration with the proposed framework, we start from the design of the system cad model using *Autodesk inventor*. The estimate of the components' mass and moment of inertia has been performed using *iProperties toolbox* from Autodesk. After estimating the UAV parameters, a prototype is generated in the simulator, as illustrated in Figure 9. In the AERO-CAM platform, a standard control architecture for hexacopter is then integrated into the digital platform. This control architecture, similar to the one proposed in [19], is composed of cascade control loops, which are responsible for maintaining the aircraft's desired position and orientation, while also ensuring the precise and stable flight of the UAV. This UAV is also equipped with a camera mounted on a 3-axis camera stabilizer, *Gremsy T3* to control the camera pose while performing inspection flights. With AIRFRAME, it is possible to add the component in the prototype, thanks to the servo model plugin, as mentioned in section II. To control the three servos, we design a control architecture in Simulink that computes the servo reference angles based on the data provided by the sensors mounted on the UAV. A sample of a flight test is provided in Figures 10 and 11. In this test, a sample trajectory has been given to the UAV, and the servo references for the camera servos have been computed automatically by the controller so that the camera can always point in the same direction. It is important to make some observations: first, a decrease in *servo 1* angles at roughly 30 sec can be noticed. This fact is due to the compensation for the increase in the UAV yaw angle. Secondly, despite some initial oscillations at the beginning of the test (when AERO-CAM was on the ground), the system is able to achieve the prescribed angles.

C. Omnidirectional platform

As last use case scenario, an omnidirectional UAV (OMAV) prototype is presented, in particular, we consider the drone

Fig. 10. Flight test performed with AERO-CAM, after the integration of the flight controller and the servo controller. The three plots provide the reference values (in blue) and the measured data (in black) of X position, Y position, Z position and yaw rate respectively. On the bottom, the tracking performance of the yaw rate of the UAV is provided as well.

Fig. 11. Analysis on gimbal servo motion during flight test whose data are provided in Figure 10. Data are provided for the reference θ_{ref} (on the left) and the actual value θ (on the right) for each of the three servos. In particular, *servo 1* is the servo at the base on the gimbal, while *servo 2* and *servo 3* are the ones on top.

presented in [21]. The prototype is integrated with an odometry sensor and an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) sensor to enhance its navigation capabilities. A control architecture for the omnidirectional UAV has been introduced in [22], which is adopted for our prototype in AIRFRAME. This control architecture is designed using Simulink, based on the approach detailed in Section III of the presented work. The controller includes two parallel Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) based control loops, aimed at stabilizing the position and orientation of the UAV. Compared to standard UAV platforms, OMAV offers the capability of moving the drone to a desired position with the desired attitude, which is not possible with conventional UAV platforms. The integration of the odometry and IMU sensors, along with the designed control architecture, provides a high level of accuracy and control in its navigation

Fig. 12. Flight test performed with OMAV after prototype creation and integration with Simulink Flight controller. The six plots provide the reference values (in blue) and the measured data (in black) of position and the orientation of UAV.

Fig. 13. Analysis on OMAV's servos during flight test whose data are provided in Figure 12. The configuration of the servos and the frames in the OMAV is detailed in [26].

and flight capabilities. A flight test is performed to evaluate the performance of the system and its Simulink flight controller. The results are highlighted in Figures 12 and 13. The flight test consists in reaching a height of approximately 3 meters and changing the orientation of the drone to prove its stability with different configurations. In the data, it's possible to notice some oscillations during transitions between reference states, this is partially due to the presence of non-filtered noise on the sensor. Although, despite these oscillations, the designed controller is always able to reach the desired state during the whole test.

V. CONCLUSION

We presented AIRFRAME, a powerful framework to help develop a custom UAV platform. The framework allows the fast generation of prototypes for aerial platforms, integrating flight controllers and testing their flight performance under different scenarios. Some examples have been presented here

Fig. 14. Omnidirectional UAV in AIRFRAME simulator

to prove the capability of AIRFRAME among different platforms and controllers. In particular, the first example presented the usage of AIRFRAME with commercial UAVs, showing how the framework can be used to test and optimize the performance of commonly used platforms. The second example presented a standard platform that has been customized to suit specific needs, highlighting the versatility of the framework in dealing with modified systems. Additionally, this example highlights the possibility to integrate standard control architecture into the framework, providing a hint at the possibility of future integration with standard open-source autopilots such as PX4 or Ardupilot. The final examples prove the compatibility with new developed omnidirectional UAV platform, for future platform design.

The results of this study demonstrate that AIRFRAME framework is a valuable tool for designers and researchers looking to fast develop and test advanced UAV systems. Further research is needed to explore the capabilities of the framework and to integrate it with commonly used autopilot software on the market.

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